

Solvent Extraction of Cerium(III) with High Molecular Weight Amines

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The use of high molecular weight amines in the extraction of cerium(III) as EDTA complex from nearly neutral aqueous medium is reported. The extraction condition was optimised from the study of effects of several variables like concentration of amine and EDTA pH nature of diluents etc. The method has been applied for the determination of cerium in few mineral samples.

The use of high molecular weight amines as liquid anion-exchanger for the extraction of anionic metal complexes has been reviewed¹. However, only a little attention has so far been paid for the anionic extraction of lanthanides². The present communication reports an extensive study on the extraction of anionic Ce^{III}-EDTA complex by tri-n-octylamine. The applicability of the proposed method was tested by the estimation of cerium in two important minerals.

Results and Discussion

Effect of pH: The pH ranges for the extraction of cerium(III) was ascertained by carrying out the extraction from pH 1.0 to 7.0 with each of the three amines separately. Fig. 1 shows that the maximum extraction takes place at pH 4.5 (Amberlite LA-2), pH 5.0 (TOA) and pH 5.5 (Adogen-464).

Role of diluents: Various organic solvents were tested as inert diluents at a fixed pH containing equal amounts of cerium(III) (25 µg) EDTA and

amine solution. The phase volume ratio was always maintained at 1:1 to avoid emulsion formation. Benzene was found to be the most effective diluent for TOA, isoamyl alcohol for Amberlite LA-2 and carbon tetrachloride for Adogen-464. It is observed (Table 1) that the relative descending order of

TABLE 1—ROLE OF DILUENTS

Diluent	Dielectric constant	% Extraction		
		Amberlite LA-2	TOA	Adogen-464
Benzene	2.28	20.10	99.62	31.60
Toluene	2.37	24.20	97.60	35.80
Xylene	2.57	27.90	92.80	39.20
Chlorobenzene	5.62	30.60	60.10	60.10
Nitrobenzene	34.80	37.80	50.65	50.15
Carbon tetrachloride	2.24	16.65	47.90	97.40
Diethyl ether	4.33	23.90	41.50	34.80
Chloroform	4.90	67.50	40.35	30.90
Butan-1-ol	16.10	36.65	39.50	20.65
Isoamyl alcohol	14.70	95.40	37.80	25.90

Fig. 1. Effect of pH on extraction of Ce^{III} with different amines: (○) TOA, (▲) Adogen-464 and (○) Amberlite LA-2

extraction with the other solvents are not the same for all the three amines and the same order does not necessarily accord the order of their dielectric constants. The dielectric constant of the medium, has some contribution in the extraction process, since the extraction involves ion-pair formation and transfer of ion-pair into organic phase is favoured in a medium of high dielectric constant since it lowers the free energy transfer. It is not, however, the only factor determining the extraction efficiency of different solvents. Some other parameters which may contribute in the extraction process must be taken into account and a better term correlating the relative extraction order is 'solubility parameter'³

Effect of extractants concentrations: Experiments were performed using 0.005–0.06 M concentrations of all the three amines using 25 µg Ce^{III} and maintaining all other conditions the same. It was found that the amount of extraction increased with increasing amine concentration and was completed at 0.6 M Amberlite LA-2; 0.04 M TOA and 0.02 M

Adogen-464. The results (Table 2) indicate that the highest degree of extraction is possible using 0.04 M TOA.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF AMINE CONCENTRATION*

Amine M	% Extraction		
	Amberlite LA-2	TOA	Adogen- 464
0.005	37.60	42.90	65.90
0.010	50.50	62.40	72.80
0.020	56.80	73.50	97.40
0.030	63.50	89.60	97.50
0.040	70.10	99.90	97.40
0.050	76.50	99.90	—
0.060	95.40	99.90	—

*Average of three determinations.

Variation of EDTA concentration : The extraction of cerium(III) was carried out with different concentration of EDTA, keeping all other parameters affecting extraction fixed. It is observed that for a particular amine the extraction increases with increase in EDTA concentration and completed at 0.01 M for Amberlite LA-2, 0.02 M for TOA and 0.05 M for Adogen-464. The results are shown in Table 3.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF EDTA CONCENTRATION*

[EDTA] M	% Extraction		
	Amberlite LA-2	TOA	Adogen- 464
0.0025	65.60	57.90	29.35
0.0050	78.90	63.90	41.60
0.0100	95.40	80.60	50.20
0.0150	95.30	89.50	65.50
0.0200	95.40	99.60	73.60
0.0400	—	—	88.90
0.0500	—	—	97.40

*Average of three determinations.

The results clearly show that the best extraction condition is achieved by the extraction with 0.04 M TOA into benzene from a neutral aqueous solution containing Ce^{III} complexed by 0.02 M EDTA. Further experiments were continued with this system only.

Choice of stripping agent : After the extraction of cerium(III) by TOA, it was stripped with 10 ml of reagents of various concentration of NaOH, NH₃, Na₂CO₃ solution (0.2–2 mol dm⁻³), HCl, HNO₃, H₂SO₄, HBr, HClO₄ (0.2–6 mol dm⁻³); lower concentration of sulphuric acid (<0.5 mol dm⁻³) was not suitable as Ce^{III} forms stabler complex with EDTA and the complex was retained by the exchanger. Finally, it was observed that 2 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ was most suitable as stripping agent.

Metal ion concentration : Cerium(III) was extracted quantitatively in the concentration range 0.005–5.0 mg in a single extraction with TOA in benzene. The average recovery being 99.8% and relative standard deviation is ±2%.

Effect of foreign ion : The effect of several diverse ions were studied using the general extraction procedure. The tolerance limit was set as the amount of foreign ion required to effect ±2% error in the recovery of cerium (25 ppm) (ion concentration in ppm indicated in parenthesis): Na^I and K^I (5000); La^{III}, Tb^{III}, Dy^{III}, Gd^{III} and Fe^{III}; Zr^{IV}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}, Ti^{IV}, Nb^V, Ta^V and phosphate (2500 ppm); Hf^{IV}, Th^{IV}, U^{VI}, Ru^{III}, Rh^{III}, Ir^{III} and silicate (500 ppm). Even Ce^{IV} could be removed and estimated in presence of Zr^{IV} or Th^{IV} by pretreatment with H₂O₂ to convert it into Ce^{III} followed by complexation. Heavier trivalent lanthanides had little effect on Ce^{III} extraction.

The separation of cerium(III) (25 ppm) is possible in the presence of more than one foreign ions (amount in µg in parenthesis) in the following mixtures (within an error of not more than ±2%): (i) Ce^{III}(25)+Ti^{IV}(200)+Zr^{IV}(200)+Na⁺(500), (ii) Ce^{III}(25)+U^{VI}(100)+Th^{IV}(100)+Fe^{III}(150), and (iii) Ce^{III}(25)+Gd^{III}(150)+Zr^{IV}(100)+Ir^{III}(100).

Cerium(III) is known⁴ to form stable EDTA complex at pH 5. Under this condition all the coordination sites of the central metal is being occupied by multidentate ligand providing a completely dehydrated metal complex and thus facilitating its quantitative transfer into non-polar organic diluents, which is otherwise not possible due to the presence of water at coordinating site partially. In the analysis of cerium from a multicomponent mixture, this behaviour of cerium(III) has been adopted for the specific and selective removal of the metal in presence of other ions which either do not form the most stable complex or do not co-extract under this specific condition thus removing any possibility of the interferences in the estimation of the metal.

Nature of extracted species : The distribution coefficient (K_D) of Ce^{III} in present case, is the ratio of radioactivities of 2 ml of organic phase to aqueous phase. This was calculated both as a function of TOA concentration and EDTA concentration. The slopes of the straight lines obtained from the plot of log K_D against log [amine] and log K_D against log [EDTA] are 1.0 and 1.08 respectively. This implies a reaction course,

The above reaction pathway was also confirmed by the absorption spectral data. Uv-visible spectra of a saturated solution of cerium(III)–EDTA showed characteristic peaks at 260 and 223.4 nm. The organic extract of such a complex also showed absorption behaviour with sharp peaks at 250 and 223.4 nm and a slight lowering of absorbance value. Hence the same complex in aqueous phase gets transferred into benzene.

Application : The two minerals e.g. monazite and ilmenite were attacked separately and brought into solution by the usual method⁵. Ce^{III} was

extracted from the solution with tri-n-octylamine in benzene using the above procedure. Triplicate extractions were performed to ascertain quantitative transfer. The metal ion was stripped from the organic phase by H_2SO_4 (2 mol dm^{-3}) and estimated by usual spectrophotometric method⁶. Results are given in Tables 4 and 5 which show a good degree of recovery of Ce^{III} by the proposed method. It is also established that the extraction procedure is highly specific and selective for Ce^{III} since other allied cations which otherwise could cause interferences in its determination, do not co-extraction into benzene under the present condition.

TABLE 4—DETERMINATION OF CERIUM IN MINERALS

Sample	Amount taken (g)	Amount of Ce present (μg)	Amount of Ce found (μg)
Monazite	0.1	1000	910
Ilmenite	0.5	2000	1949

TABLE 5—RECOVERY OF CERIUM(III)

Sample	Amount added (μg)	Amount found (μg)	Recovery %
Ilmenite	0.0	1949	—
	100	2047	99.7
	200	2158	100.2
	300	2251	100.0
	400	2342	99.4

Experimental

Tri-n-octylamine (tertiary) (E. Merck), Amberlite LA-2 (secondary) and Adogen-464 (quaternary) (both from Aldrich) were used as such. All other reagents used were of A.R. grade. A stock solution containing 25 ppm Ce^{III} and labelled with $Ce-141$ isotope tracer (supplied by B.A.R.C., India) was prepared by the addition of tracer solution to a solution of inactive Ce^{III} in $2 N H_2SO_4$.

A Shimadzu 335 pH meter was used for pH measurements. The radioactivity was measured in a well-type scintillation counter with NaI(Tl) detector and spectrophotometric studies were carried out in a Shimadzu 160A spectrophotometer.

General extraction procedure. An aqueous solution of cerium(III) (25 ppm) kept at the requisite pH and complexed by EDTA solution of desired molarity, was equilibrated with equal volume of an organic phase containing the amine dissolved in inert solvent. After an equilibration period of 5 min, radioactivities of both the two phases (2 ml each) were separately measured and the metal ion contents computed. Amount of metal ion in organic phase could also be measured by stripping it into an aqueous phase using $2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} H_2SO_4$ and the concentration of cerium was measured by the usual colorimetric method⁷.

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